

MEDICAL SCIENCES

MOLECULAR AND GENETIC PREDICTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF DENTAL CARIES

Kotelban A.,

*PhD, Associate Professor, Chernivtsi, Ukraine,
Department of Pediatric Dentistry
Bukovynian State Medical University*

Mytchenok M.,

*PhD, Associate Professor, Chernivtsi, Ukraine,
Department of Pediatric Dentistry
Bukovynian State Medical University*

Moroz P.,

*PhD, Associate Professor, Chernivtsi, Ukraine,
Department of Surgery № 1
Bukovynian State Medical University*

Mytchenok O.

*PhD, Associate Professor, Chernivtsi, Ukraine,
Department of Therapeutic Dentistry,
Bukovinian State Medical University*

Abstract

Various factors, both internal and external, lead to the development of caries. Today, the study of molecular genetic predictors of disease, including dental caries, has become widespread.

In this regard, we searched for literature sources in domestic and foreign scientometric databases in order to study the current state of the molecular genetic mechanisms of dental caries.

Numerous studies have established the role of inheritance of dental caries and identified the main genes that ensure the resistance of enamel to cariogenic factors, the completeness of the composition of saliva and the rate of salivation.

Keywords: caries, molecular and genetic determinants, amelogenesis genes, dentinogenesis genes.

Dental caries is complex, chronic, polyetiological, one of the most common diseases in industrialized and developing countries [1].

The development of caries is caused by the influence of fermented carbohydrates on the biofilm of the teeth, which causes the accumulation of cariogenic bacteria, such as *Streptococcus mutans*, *S. sobrinus*, as well as some species of *Lactobacillus*. Prolonged exposure to the acids produced by these bacteria, combined with the limited buffering capacity of the oral fluid, causes calcium loss from the teeth [2].

On the basis of scientific research, not only the role of molecular genetic markers, but also the influence of external and internal environmental factors on the development of caries are obvious. As external factors leading to the development of caries, the following should be considered: demographic, such as age, gender, ethnicity and level of education; anthropometric, including height, body mass index, waist circumference; environmental factors, including diet, frequency of brushing teeth, water quality, level of fluoride content in water [4]. Presumably, external factors include the composition of the microbiota of the oral cavity: biofilms of teeth and saliva. It is known that women suffer from dental caries more often than men [5]. Among the environmental factors, the fluoride content in the consumed water and the level of oral hygiene are the most significant. Socio-economic factors are also important, such as the level of education in the family, which determines the understanding of the role of oral hygiene and rational observance of the rules of personal

hygiene to preserve teeth [5-8]. An important role is played by the individual's diet and taste preferences, in particular the consumption of sweet food [9]. As an external factor, it should also be noted environmental pollution, especially pronounced in industrial regions and megacities, which can affect the state of tooth enamel and thus contribute to the development of caries [10].

Internal factors include genetic factors, features of tooth morphology, saliva composition and rate of saliva secretion, etc. Studies of the inheritance of dental caries in children using the twin method have clearly shown the key role of genetic markers in the development of the disease. The estimate of inheritance of caries by the twin method was from 64 to 85%, according to some data it is slightly lower - from 40 to 60% [11]. Inheritance of caries for milk teeth exceeds 50%. The influence of various factors in different age groups of children, for example, in preschool and school age, is often different, which involves consideration of the spectrum of factors that determine the development of dental caries, depending on age [12]. The Vipeholm study provided evidence of the resistance of the hard tissues of the subjects' teeth to caries, despite the fact that they followed a highly cariogenic diet. This suggests that caries susceptibility or resistance may result from one or more genotypes, phenotypes, and environmental influences. In the scientific literature, the incidence of dental caries has long been associated with heredity [13].

As early as 1899, Black GV wrote that when the family remains in one settlement, and the children live

in conditions similar to those of their parents in childhood, the tendency to caries in most cases will be the same. This applies even to individual groups of teeth, settlements in which people first suffered from caries, the order in which caries occur, and the specific age at which they occur [14].

Tooth enamel is considered to be the most mineralized tissue in vertebrates, which is characterized by high strength and high compactness. Enamel formation is the result of a series of ectomesenchymal interactions. Enamel defects occur as a result of disturbances in the formation of teeth and can lead to changes in the formation of enamel or calcification of the organic matrix. Defects in the formation of enamel affect the development of dental caries. Insufficiently mineralized or irregularly structured enamel can lead to the development of caries. Defects in tooth enamel can be caused not only by genetic markers, but also by environmental factors. The general term "amelogenesis imperfecta" is used to denote any disorders of tooth enamel at the stage of tooth development before eruption: thinned (hypoplasia), undercalcified (very soft) and immature (discolored and soft, but of normal thickness) enamel; all such enamel disorders contribute to the development of caries [15].

Hydroxyapatite crystals are based on a number of molecules of the organic matrix, which includes amelogenin, enamelin, ameloblastin, taftelin, which are the basis of the organic matrix of enamel, and sialophosphoprotein of dentin [16]. The ameloblastin gene (AMBN) is located on chromosome 4 [17] and is a key molecule for enamel formation and plays an important role in binding and maintaining the differentiated phenotypes of secretory ameloblasts [18]. Taftelin acts at the initial stages of mineralization, and its overexpression can lead to imperfections in both enamel prisms and crystallite structure [19]. Hydroxyapatite crystals are based on a number of molecules of the organic matrix, which includes amelogenin, enamelin, ameloblastin, taftelin, which are the basis of the organic matrix of enamel, and sialophosphoprotein of dentin [16]. The ameloblastin gene (AMBN) is located on chromosome 4 [17] and is a key molecule for enamel formation and plays an important role in binding and maintaining the differentiated phenotypes of secretory ameloblasts [18]. Taftelin acts at the initial stages of mineralization, and its overexpression can lead to imperfections in both enamel prisms and crystallite structure [19].

The amelogenin gene (AMELX) is located on the p arm of the X chromosome, and its locus is Xp22.31-p22.1 [16]. Previously, the gene was also known by the designations: AMG, AI1E, AIH1, ALGN, AMGL and AMGX [15]. It forms a framework for enamel crystallites and controls their growth [22]. Alternative splicing has been described for the amelogenin gene [23]. Alternative splicing of the primary RNA transcript of amelogenin is the main feature of amelogenin biosynthesis with exon skipping and utilization of alternative 3'-acceptor sites in exons, which explains the diversity of amelogenin mRNA [24].

The DSPP (dentin-sialophosphoprotein) gene encodes the two most important dentin proteins of the outer matrix of the tooth: preproprotein (secreted by

odontoblasts and transformed into dentin sialoprotein) and dentin phosphoprotein [25]. It is believed that dentin phosphoprotein is involved in the process of biomineralization of dentin [26].

A number of mutations affecting the structure of dentin have been identified, individual and interspecies variability in the length of the DSP domain has been noted, which in humans ranges from 770 to 902 amino acids [25]. In some families with DSPP gene mutations, the formation of softer abnormal dentin is shown, which is always accompanied by an increased risk of caries development [26]. For the T rs2615487 (C/T) allele of the DSPP gene, a highly reliable protective effect on the disease was demonstrated [27].

Defects in these genes are associated with many diseases. Mutation of dentin sialophosphoprotein gene causes imperfect dentinogenesis type II [28, 29]. Rajpar et al [30] observed that splicing disruption in the gene encoding the enamel-specific protein enamelin caused autosomal dominant amelogenesis imperfecta. Kim et al [26] observed in families with a dentin sialophosphoprotein mutation that softer deformed dentin was always associated with an increased risk of oral disease. Thus, mutations in these genes lead to the translation of abnormal proteins or reduce the amount of these proteins in developing teeth, leading to defective mineralization that can affect both the degree of bacterial adhesion and the resistance of enamel to acidic pH, thereby increasing susceptibility of enamel to caries.

In addition to defective mineralization, genotypic variations also make enamel more vulnerable. Shimuzu et al [20] suggest that variations in enamel-forming genes affect the dynamic interactions between the enamel surface and the oral cavity. The frequency of the T allele of the AMELX gene (rs946252) and the C allele of AMBN (rs4694075) was significantly higher in the high caries group. They also observed that taftelin-interacting protein 11 is associated with the ability of the enamel surface to absorb fluoride at very low concentrations, thus reducing individual susceptibility to demineralization at subclinical levels. Similar findings were observed by Kang et al. [31] in a study of Korean residents who lived in regions with high levels of fluoride during childhood, that single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in variants rs5933871 and rs5934997 of the AMELX gene were significantly associated with caries susceptibility. A significant connection between taftelin and amelogenin with increased susceptibility to dental caries was reported by Patir et al. [16], Slayton et al. [32] and Deeley et al. [33] for caries. Differential genetic factors on the enamel surface of deciduous and permanent teeth, as well as the presence of pits and fissures or a smooth enamel surface, also contribute to the development of carious lesions. Shaffer et al observed that the inheritance of caries with pits and fissures and with a smooth surface in deciduous teeth was greater than in the permanent dentition. It was also highlighted that common genes are involved in caries risk for both surface types. However, genetic factors have a different effect on caries risk in pits and fissures compared to smooth enamel surfaces in primary dentition [34].

A significant heritability of caries in deciduous dentition (54–70%) compared to permanent teeth (35–55%) with covariation of these traits due to common genetic factors was reported by Wang et al. The notion that genes differentially affect cariogenesis on different surfaces was also confirmed by Zeng et al [22], who identified several potential caries genes, namely the BCOR gene in pitted and fissured surface caries and BCORL1 in smooth enamel caries. surface [12]. One of the few studies of nucleotide polymorphisms in genes (dentin sialophosphoprotein, kallikrein 4 and aquaporin 5) showed a consistent association with caries protection of pitted and fissured caries and caries with a smooth surface in 333 Caucasians. However, the minor allele (G) of kallikrein 4 was associated with an increased risk of smooth surface enamel caries [27].

The development of caries is also influenced by the features of tooth morphology [35], for example, hard-to-clean tooth surfaces may be more prone to caries. A greater susceptibility to caries of chewing surfaces compared to other tooth surfaces has also been demonstrated, however, according to some authors, lesions of different tooth surfaces are correlated [27, 36]. As an important factor affecting the development of caries, the composition of saliva and the rate of salivation can be identified, since saliva contains components that directly destroy bacteria that cause the development of the carious process. In particular, it was shown that a low concentration of alpha-defensin in saliva was correlated with a high level of caries [29].

Saliva is also involved in the process of remineralization of tooth enamel, as it contains a lot of calcium and phosphates. The flow of saliva helps wash away pathogens (viruses, bacteria, and yeast) from the surface of the teeth and the oral mucosa [30]. So, the more intense the salivation, the better the protection of the teeth from harmful effects.

Genes determining the process of salivation include the aquaporin-5 (AQP5) gene, which is responsible for the generation of tears, saliva, and fluid secretion in the lungs [32]. Also, this gene, together with the aquaporin-4 gene, participated in the hydration of the extracellular matrix in the process of tooth formation. The role of the AQP5 gene in the development of caries is associated with a decrease in the amount of saliva [37].

Associations with the development of caries have been established for the lactotransferrin gene [34, 35]. The product of the gene is a glycoprotein that is present in various biological fluids. Lactotransferrin is able to affect the dental biofilm, preventing the adhesion of *S. mutans*, provides an antibacterial immune response of the host, and also promotes protection against *Candida albicans*, a pathogen that serves as an important component of the dental biofilm and is associated with early caries, as it produces acids and is resistant to them [38].

Conclusion. Various factors affect the development of caries. Molecular genetic mechanisms of caries development are relevant and scientifically based today. Numerous studies have established the role of the inheritance of dental caries and identified the main genes that ensure the completeness of the morphology of the teeth, the composition of saliva and the rate of

saliva secretion, enamel resistance to cariogenic factors.

Conflict of interest. Missing.

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